

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

VALIDATED STABILITY INDICATING RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE DETERMINATION OF FIMASARTAN IN PRESENCE OF DEGRADATION PRODUCTS

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 30/11/2017
Available online
06/12/2017

Keywords

Fimasartan,
RP-HPLC,
Stability Indicating Assay
Method (SIAM's),
ICH Q1A(R2),
Q2R1.

ABSTRACT

A simple, isocratic, specific and sensitive stability-indicating high-performance liquid chromatographic method was developed and validated for the determination of fimasartan in synthetic mixture. Fimasartan is used to treat hypertension. Reverse phase chromatography was performed on Shimadzu LC-20AD pump (binary) and Shimadzu PDA-M20A Diode Array Detector using Hypersil BDS C18 column (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m) mobile phase containing Phosphate buffer pH3 :Acetonitrile (50:50, v/v) with a flow rate of 1ml/min. Detection was done at wavelength 262nm. Linearity was observed in the concentration range of 5-30 μ g/mL ($R^2=0.999$) with regression equation $y=78487x+66095$. The LOD was found to be 1.54 μ g/ml and LOQ was found to be 4.67 μ g/ml. Fimasartan was subjected to stress conditions such as acidic, alkaline, oxidation, photolysis and thermal degradations. The proposed method was validated as per ICH guideline and was found to be accurate, precise and specific. The degradation products peaks were well resolved from the standard drug peak and hence this method can be used for quality control of fimasartan. The drug showed significant degradation in alkaline and oxidative condition. Degradation products in alkaline and oxidative conditions were identified by LC-MS. Oxidative degradation followed first order kinetic. Degradation rate constants and half -lives were determined.

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Please cite this article in press as **Charu P. Pandya et al. Validated Stability Indicating RP-HPLC Method for the Determination of Fimasartan in Presence of Degradation Products. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2017:7(11).**

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INTRODUCTION

Fimasartan belongs to the class of non-peptide angiotensin II receptor antagonist (ARB). It is used for the treatment of hypertension and heart failure. Fimasartan blocks angiotensin II receptor type (AT1 receptors), reduces prohypertensive actions of angiotensin II such as systemic vasoconstriction and water retention by the kidneys. Fimasartan was approved in South Korea in September 9, 2010. It was developed by Boryung Pharmaceuticals with brand name of Kanarb. The chemical name of Fimasartan is 2-butyl-5-dimethyl aminothiocarboxymethyl-6-methyl-3[(2'-(1H-tetrazol-5-yl) biphenyl-4-yl)methyl]pyrimidin-4(3H)-one potassium trihydrate. Molecular weight of fimasartan is 593.79. Losartan which is the first drug in ARB class, contains imidazole ring, replacement of imidazole with pyrimidinone moiety tethering with biphenyl tetrazole at its 3-position results in formation of fimasartan [1]. HPLC method has been developed for evaluation of stability and simultaneous determination of fimasartan and amlodipine in tablet dosage form [5]. UPLC tandem mass chromatographic method has been developed for determination of fimasartan in human plasma [6]. LC-MS methods have been reported for the estimation of fimasartan in human plasma [7-9]. Pharmacokinetics and metabolite profiling of fimasartan has been reported [10]. The need to develop a stability indicating method using stress degradation has been recommended by International Conference of Harmonization. The stress conditions should include the effect of temperature, humidity, light, oxidizing agents and susceptibility across wide range of pH values. An ideal stability indicating method is one that quantifies the drug and resolves its degradation products [12]. To the best of our knowledge stability indicating method of fimasartan is not reported. In the present study, a simple, rapid, precise and accurate stability indicating liquid chromatographic method was developed for the determination of fimasartan in synthetic mixture and validated as per ICH guidelines. Stress degradation was performed to determine the most potential degradation related impurities. The validated method was applied to study the rate of FIMA oxidative degradation.

Figure 1- Structure of Fimasartan Potassium Trihydrate.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemical Reagents and solutions :

Fimasartan standard drug was purchased from Angene Chemical Ltd (China). Acetonitrile (HPLC grade) was purchased from Rankem Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai. HPLC grade Potassium dihydrogen ortho phosphate, phosphoric acid was purchased from Loba Cheme Pvt. Ltd. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH), Hydrochloric acid (HCl) and Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) were obtained from S.D. Fine Chemical Ltd, Mumbai.

Preparation of mobile phase:

A 10 mM phosphate buffer was prepared by dissolving 1.37 g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in sufficient water to produce 1000 ml and then the pH 3.0 was adjusted with orthophosphoric acid. Mobile phase was prepared with phosphate buffer and acetonitrile in the ratio of 50:50.

Instrumentation and chromatographic conditions:

HPLC –UV:

Chromatography was performed on Shimadzu (Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan) chromatographic system equipped with Shimadzu LC-20AD pump (binary) and Shimadzu PDA-M20A Diode Array Detector. Samples were injected through Rheodyne 7725 injector valve with a fixed loop at 20 µL. Data acquisition and integration were performed using LC Solution software (Shimadzu Corporation, Japan). Separation and quantitation were made on a Hypersil BDS C 18 column (5 µm x 250mm x 4.6 mm i.d.). The flow rate was at 1.0 ml/min at ambient column temperature and effluent was detected at 262 nm. Before use, the mobile phase was filtered through a 0.2 µ nylon membrane filter and sonicated for 5 min.

LC-MS (Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy):

An LC-MS system (thermo Scientific, Sunnyvale, CA, USA) comprised of a LCQ Fleet Ion Trap Mass Spectrometer. The analysis was performed in positive electro-spray/positive ionization mode with an ion source voltage of 5000 V and a source temperature of 450°C. The curtain gas flow was 20 psi. The data was collected and processed using Surveyor plus HPLC System with Qual browser software. Phosphate buffer in HPLC UV was replaced by 0.1 % formic acid. Mobile phase was prepared by adding 1ml of formic acid in 1000 ml of water and other HPLC conditions were matched as those described in HPLC-UV analysis.

Preparation of Fimasartan stock solution:

FIMA stock solution (1000 µg/ml) was prepared by accurately weighing 25 mg of FIMA in a 25 ml volumetric flask and making upto volume with HPLC grade water and acetonitrile (50 :50). Working standard solution (100 µg/ml) was prepared from stock solution in a solvent mixture of phosphate buffer-acetonitrile (50:50, v/v) (mobile phase). Working standard solution was further diluted to get the concentration range of 5-30µg/ml.

Method Validation:

The proposed method was validated according to the ICH guidelines for system suitability, specificity, recovery, precision, linearity, robustness, limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ). Under the validation study, various parameters were studied.

System suitability:

System suitability test should be carried out to verify that the analytical system is working properly and can give accurate and precise results. Working standard solutions were prepared and injected six times into the chromatographic system. The system suitability parameters were evaluated for peak area, retention time, tailing factor and theoretical plates of standard chromatograms.

Linearity and Range:

The linearity of method was evaluated thrice by analyzing prepared concentrations of FIMA in the range of 5-30µg/ml from the stock solution. 20µl of each solution was injected into HPLC system and the peak area of the chromatogram obtained was noted. Linear regression equation was obtained over the concentration range ($y=mx+c$).

Precision:

The intra-day precision of the assay method was evaluated at six concentration levels (5-30µg/ml) (n=6) against a qualified reference standard. % RSD of three obtained assay values at six different concentration levels was calculated. The inter-day precision study was performed on three different days i.e. day 1, day 2 and day 3 at six different concentration levels (5-30µg/ml) and each value is the average of three determinations (n=3). The % RSD of the three obtained assay values on three different days was calculated.

Accuracy:

The % recovery was performed by standard addition method. In this method fixed amount of sample mixture of FIMA and increasing amount of its working standard solutions were added at 80, 100 and 120 % level of pure drug solution. Standard addition and recovery experiments were conducted to determine the accuracy of the method for the quantification of FIMA in the drug product. The study was carried out in triplicate at 16, 20 and 24 µg/ml and percentage recovery in each case was calculated.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of quantification (LOQ) :

The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were based on the standard deviation of the response and the slope of the constructed calibration curve (n=3), as described in International Conference on Harmonization guidelines Q2 (R1) [14]. Sensitivity of the method was established with respect to limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) for FIMA.

Robustness:

The robustness of the assay method was established by introducing small changes in the HPLC conditions which included , pH of buffer (2.8,3.2), flow rate (0.9 and 1.1 ml/min), percentage of acetonitrile in the mobile phase (48 and 52%). Robustness of the method was studied using three replicates at a concentration level of 10µg/mL of FIMA.

Solution stability:

The solution stability of FIMA was carried out by leaving the sample solution in tightly capped volumetric flasks at room temperature for 48 h. The sample solutions were assayed at 24 h intervals over the study period. The %RSD of FIMA was calculated. An additional study was carried out using the stock solution by storing it in a tightly capped volumetric flask at 4°C.

Analysis of synthetic mixture:

The synthetic mixture equivalent to 60mg of FIMA was taken into 100ml volumetric flask, 30ml of water and acetonitrile (50:50) was taken. This was shaken and sonicated for 15 minutes. Volume was made with water and acetonitrile (50:50). The solution was filtered with Whatman filter paper no-1 (FIMA- 600µg/ml). Working sample preparation - 1ml from sample stock solution was taken into 10ml volumetric flask and volume was made with mobile phase (FIMA-60µg/ml). The resulting solution was filtered using 0.45µ filter. 20µl of the solution was injected and chromatogram was recorded under optimized chromatographic conditions and peak area was measured. The assay procedure was made in triplicate and % drug was calculated.

Force degradation study:

Force degradation studies of FIMA were performed under acid,alkaline,neutral,oxidative, thermal and photolytic conditions. Force degradation studies were performed to evaluate the stability indicating properties and specificity of the method [15]. For force degradation study, stock solution of FIMA is prepared by dissolving 25mg of FIMA in 25ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume with diluents of water and acetonitrile.

Acidic degradation:

Acidic degradation was performed by treating 2.5 mL of stock solution of FIMA with 1N hydrochloric acid for 3 hours in a water bath at 100°C, cooled and then the stressed sample was neutralized and diluted with diluents and filtered with 0.45 µ syringe filter as per the requirement before injecting into the HPLC system.

Alkaline degradation:

Alkaline degradation was performed by treating 2.5 mL of stock solution of FIMA with 1N sodium hydroxide for 4 hours in a water bath at 100°C, cooled and then the stressed sample was neutralized and diluted with diluents and filtered with 0.45µ syringe filter as per the requirement before injecting into the HPLC system.

Neutral hydrolytic degradation:

Neutral hydrolytic degradation was performed by treating 2.5 mL of stock solution of FIMA with water for 4 hours in a water bath at 100°C, cooled and sample was diluted with diluents and filtered with 0.45µ syringe filter as per the requirement before injecting into the HPLC system.

Oxidative degradation:

Oxidative degradation was performed by treating 2.5 mL of stock solution of FIMA with 0.9% hydrogen peroxide at room temperature for 30 minutes and diluted with diluents and filtered with 0.45µ syringe filter as per the requirement before injecting into the HPLC system.

Thermal degradation:

Thermal degradation was performed by placing 25 mg of FIMA in 25 mL of volumetric flask in oven at 80°C for 8 days. FIMA was diluted with diluents and final concentration was made upto 100µg/mL.

Photolytic degradation:

Photolytic degradation (dry) was performed by placing 25 mg of FIMA in 25 mL of volumetric flask in photo stability chamber for 21 days. FIMA was diluted with diluents and final concentration was made upto 100µg/mL. Photolytic degradation in solution (1mg/mL) for photo stability testing was exposed to UV light in photolytic chamber for 21 days and then analyzed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

The present work was aimed to develop a stability indicating RP-HPLC method for the determination of FIMA in presence of its degradation products. A reverse-phase chromatographic technique was developed to determine FIMA at 262nm and C 18 column was adopted for the analysis.

HPLC method development and optimization:

Proper selection of the method depends upon the nature of the sample (ionizable or neutral molecule), its molecular weight and solubility. The analytical conditions such as diluents, buffer, buffer concentration, organic solvent were selected for mobile phase and mobile phase compositions. Preliminary trials were taken with different ratio of water-methanol, water-acetonitrile, different compositions of buffer and organic phase of mobile phase with pH range of 2.5-4. The column selection has been done by backpressure, resolution, peak shape, theoretical plates and day-to-day reproducibility. After evaluating all these factors, Hypersil BDS C 18 column was found to be giving satisfactory results. The selection of acetonitrile and buffer were based on chemical structure of FIMA. The acidic pH range was found to be suitable for solubility, stability, theoretical plates and day-to-day reproducibility. Best results were obtained with orthophosphoric acid pH adjusted to 3.0 that improved the peak shape of FIMA. For selection of organic constituent of mobile phase, acetonitrile was chosen to reduce the longer retention time and to attain good peak shape. Therefore, final mobile phase composition consisting of a mixture of buffer-pH 3.0 (10 mm phosphate buffer): acetonitrile (50:50). Optimized method was providing good resolution and peak shape for FIMA. Under above described experimental conditions, all the peaks were well defined and free from tailing.

Method Validation:**System suitability:**

The retention time of FIMA using optimum conditions was 7.306 min. For all of them, the peak symmetries were < 1.5 and theoretical plates were > 2000 and % RSD of areas of six standard injections of FIMA was less than 2. These values are within the acceptable range of United States of pharmacopoeia definition and the chromatographic conditions. The results obtained were shown in Table 1.

Table 1- System suitability parameter of FIMA.

Parameter	Value \pm SD*
Peak Area	568309.3 \pm 0.85
Theoretical Plates	10689.82 \pm 123.79
Retention time	7.306 \pm 0.052
Tailing factor	1.224 \pm 0.018

(SD - Standard Deviation).

Linearity:

The calibration curve for FIMA was linear over the concentration range 5-30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The data for the peak area of the drug corresponding to the concentration was treated by linear regression analysis (Table 2) and the regression equation for the calibration curve was found to be $y = 4847x + 66095$ with correlation coefficient of 0.999 which is nearly equals to unity Figure 2 (A). The typical chromatograms for FIMA obtained from the bulk and extracted marketed formulations were shown in Figure 2(B)-2(C).

Table 2- Linearity of FIMA.

Level	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak Area
1	5	279143
2	10	571035
3	15	792567
4	20	1061278
5	25	1290123
6	30	1527890

Figure 2 (A) – Calibration curve of FIMA.

Figure 2 (B) – Chromatogram of FIMA (20 µg/mL).

Figure 2 (C) – Chromatogram of FIMA synthetic mixture (20 µg/mL).

Precision:

The precision of the method was determined by repeatability (intra-day precision) and intermediate precision of FIMA standard solutions. Repeatability was calculated by assaying three samples of each six different concentrations (5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) on the same day. The inter-day precision calculated by assaying three samples of each at six different concentrations (5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) on three consecutive days. % RSD in precision studies was found to be 0.85 (intra-day) (Table 3) and 1.12 (inter-day) (< 2%) (Table 4).

Table 3- Intra day precision of FIMA.

Conc.($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Area 1	Area 2	Area 3	Mean	%RSD
5	288165	286762	282043	285656.7	1.12
10	570104	572092	562852	568349.3	0.85
15	802460	812578	810327	808455	0.65
20	1051365	1067476	1054634	1057825	0.80
25	1281873	1260741	1278207	1273607	0.88
30	1518083	1493457	1503145	1504895	0.82
			Average		0.85

Table 4- Inter day Precision of FIMA.

Conc.($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Day1	Day 2	Day3	Mean	%RSD
5	287134	288165	280567	285288.7	1.44
10	570104	573789	561031	568309.3	1.15
15	802460	813567	803678	806568.3	0.75
20	1051365	1062836	1073214	1062472	1.02
25	1281873	1260584	1249064	1263840	1.3
30	1518083	1486788	150235	1502405	1.04
			Average		1.12

(RSD – Relative Standard Deviation).

Accuracy:

The method accuracy was proved by the recovery studies. A known amount of FIMA standard (20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was added to aliquots of sample solutions and then diluted to yield total concentrations as 36, 40, 44 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The resultant recovery was 98.75-100.8% (Table 5).

Table 5- Accuracy study of FIMA.

% spiking	Actual concentration of FIMA($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount of FIMA added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	*Amount of FIMA recovered ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Recovery \pm SD
80%	20	16	15.80	98.75% \pm 0.057735
100%	20	20	9.9	99.02% \pm 0.060828
120%	20	24	24.19	100.8% \pm 0.057735

(SD- Standard Deviation) *Mean of three replicates.

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ):

The LOD was found to be 1.54 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and LOQ was found to be 4.67 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Robustness:

The developed RP-HPLC method was also found to be robust when small changes were induced in the method parameters which can be seen in Table 6. pH of buffer, flow rate, % of acetonitrile were varied. Peak area and retention time were noted. Standard deviation was calculated, which was found to be less than 2 indicating that the method is robust.

Table 6- Robustness study of FIMA.

Factor	*Retention Time	*Peak Area
pH of buffer		
2.8	7.309	561074
3.0	7.425	572984
3.2	7.313	572987
Mean \pm SD	7.325 \pm 0.008327	569015 \pm 1.208
Flow Rate		
0.9	8.122	568903
1.0	7.327	570136
1.1	6.670	560032
Mean \pm SD	7.405 \pm 0.726	566690.3 \pm 1.034
B. % of Acetonitrile		
48	8.276	568345
50	7.382	579264
52	6.488	571934
Mean \pm SD	7.382 \pm 0.894	573181 \pm 0.97

(SD- Standard Deviation) *Mean of three replicates.

Solution stability:

Solution stability was determined by monitoring peak area response. Standard stock solutions in diluents were analyzed in different time comparing to the response obtained for freshly prepared solutions. No significant changes(2%) were observed according to the peak area responses for the stock solution stores at 4°C for two weeks, relative to freshly prepared standards. The stability of sample was tested for every 6 hr interval upto 24 hr. The RSD value of FIMA was 0.013% (Table 7). This indicated that the sample solution was stable upto 24 hr.

Table 7- Analysis of FIMA solution stability.

Time(Hrs)	Area	Mean	SD	% RSD
6	573789	573408.6	7587.562	0.013232
12	561035			
18	578292			
24	579824			

(SD – Standard Deviation) (RSD- Relative Standard Deviation)

Analysis of marketed formulation (tablets):

The proposed method was applied for the determination of FIMA in marketed formulations (tablets) and the % recovery was found to be 98.8-99.3 (Table 8).

Table 8- Analysis of FIMA marketed solution.

S.No.	Label Claim	Result	% Assay	Mean	SD	%RSD
1	60mg	59.4 mg	99	99.03	0.251	0.254
2	60mg	59.6 mg	99.3			
3	60 mg	59.3mg	98.8			

(SD – Standard Deviation) (RSD- Relative Standard Deviation).

Selectivity/Specificity:

The specificity of the developed method was determined by injecting sample solutions (100 μ g/mL) which were prepared by degradation under stress conditions such as heat, oxidative, acid and base under proposed chromatographic conditions.

Force degradation studies:

Stress testing of drug substance can help in identifying the likely degradation products which can establish the degradation pathways and the intrinsic stability of the molecule. The nature of the stress testing will depend on the individual drug substance. The chromatograms obtained from the samples treated with acid, alkaline, oxidative, and thermal and photo degradation were examined. Degradation of FIMA was found to be similar for both the mixture and standard. Typical chromatograms obtained following assay of stressed samples are shown in Figure 3(A)-3(H). Degradation was not observed in thermal and photolytic (dry) conditions. A very slight degradation (<2.5%) was seen on exposure of the drug solution to acidic, photolytic solutions. Degradation in alkaline was found to be 9.1% and in oxidative conditions 29.9% (Table 9). It indicates that FIMA is susceptible towards oxidative and alkaline degradation.

Figure 3(A) – Chromatogram of FIMA (100µg/ml).

Figure 3 (B) – Chromatogram of acid degraded sample.

Figure 3 (C) – Chromatogram of alkaline degraded sample (Zoomed View).

Figure 3 (D) – Chromatogram of alkaline degraded sample (Full View).

Figure 3 (E) – Chromatogram of oxidative degraded sample.

Figure 3 (F) – Chromatogram of thermal degraded sample.

Figure 3(G) - Chromatogram of photolytic degraded sample (Dry).

Figure 3 (H) – Chromatogram of photolytic degraded sample (solution).

Table 9- Force degradation study of FIMA.

Stress Condition	Temperature (°C)	Time (Hrs)	RT of Degradants	% of Degradants in API	% of Degradants in synthetic mixture
Hydrolytic					
Acid	100°C	3 hrs	4.9 min (DP4)	0.5%	0/1%
Base	100°C	4hrs	3.1 min (DP1)	9.1%	8.8%
			3.9 min (DP2)		
			4.2 min(DP3)		
			4.8min (DP4)		
			6.1 min (DP5)		
Neutral	100°C	4 hrs	--	--	--
Thermal	80°C	8 days	--	--	--
Photolytic	5382 Lux and 144UW/cm ²	21 days			
Dry			--	---	--
Solution			4.9 min(DP4)	0.5%	

The identification of degradation products was also effective for knowing the degradation pathways of drug substance. Therefore the degradation products of alkaline and oxidative conditions were subjected to LC-MS study to elucidate structural details. Results are tabulated in Table 10 and mass spectra are shown in figure 4(A)-4(D). Mass spectra of FIMA was observed at m/z 502.33, degradation product DP2 is obtained with m/z 459.1, DP4 with m/z 486.25, DP5 with m/z 475.17.

Table 10- Characterization of degradation products by LC-MS.

Compound	m/z	Structure	Systematic name
FIMA	502.33		2-butyl-5-dimethylaminothiocarbonylmethyl-6-methyl-3-[[2'-(1H-tetrazol-5-yl)biphenyl-4-yl]methylpyrimidin-4(3H)-one
DP2	459.1		2-(1-((2'-(2H-tetrazol-5-yl)-[1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl)methyl)-2-butyl-4-methyl-6-oxo-1,6-dihydropyrimidin-5-yl)acetic acid
DP4	486.25		2-(1-((2'-(2H-tetrazol-5-yl)-[1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl)methyl)-2-butyl-4-methyl-6-oxo-1,6-dihydropyrimidin-5-yl)-N,N-dimethylacetamide
DP5	475.17		2-(1-(2'-(2H-tetrazol-5-yl)-[1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl)methyl)-2-butyl-4-methyl-6-oxo-1,6-dihydropyrimidin-5-yl)ethanethioamidium

Figure 4 (A) – Mass spectra of FIMA.

Figure 4 (B) – Mass spectra of DP2.

Figure 4 (C) – Mass spectra of DP4.

Figure 4 (D) – Mass spectra of DP5.

Degradation kinetic study

A regular decrease in the concentration of FIMA with increasing time intervals was observed in oxidative degradation of FIMA. Calculations have been based on measurement of the concentration of the Drug remaining using the previously described HPLC-UV method. At the selected temperature and time-interval (Table 11) degradation process followed first order kinetics Figure 5(A)-5(B). A regular decrease in the percentage of the drug with increasing time was observed. From the slope of the straight lines, it was possible to calculate degradation rate constants and half-lives ($t_{1/2}$) at each temperature based on the equation .

Table 11- Kinetic data – Degradation rate constants & half –lives for oxidative degradation.

Stressor	Temperature	Concentration	Regression Equation	R ²	Deg. Rate constant (moles/l/hr) K	t _{1/2} (hrs)
H ₂ O ₂	RT	0.9%	y=0.143x+1.932	0.981	0.324	2.10
	60°C	0.9%	y=-0.229x+2.032	0.964	0.524	1.31
	RT	3.0%	y=-0.431x+2.120	0.990	0.993	0.69
	60°C	3.0%	Y=-0.5806x+2.1212	0.993	1.342	1.22

Figure 5(A) – First order kinetics of 0.9% H₂O₂.

Figure 5 (B) – First order kinetics of 3 % H₂O₂.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

None

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are grateful to Faculty of Pharmacy, M.S. University, Baroda, India for providing research facilities to carry out this work.

CONCLUSION

The developed HPLC technique for the determination of FIMA is precise, specific accurate and stability indicating. Drug peak was well separated in presence of degradation products. The data showed that the excipients and degradation products did not interfere with the FIMA peak, indicating selectivity of the method. The proposed stability indicating method was validated as per ICH guidelines. Degradation of FIMA was observed in alkaline and oxidative conditions. The structure of degradation related impurities were determined. Kinetic studies showed oxidative degradation followed first order kinetics.

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